

Geotechnical failures: A personal perspective

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ABSTRACT: Geotechnical engineering is both an art and a science as it combines the application of scientific principles with engineering judgement. Such judgement is required because of incomplete and uncertain information but is also critically dependent on the experience of the engineer for any particular application. Experience is greatly enhanced by the lessons learnt from past mistakes. However, all too often, engineering mistakes are not commonly advertised because of reputational damage to the companies involved or to 'deals' emerging from litigation. To address this deficiency, this paper describes simple examples of 'geotechnical failures' that the author has had direct experience of during his 40-year career as a geotechnical engineer. Standard 'text book' type problems are rarely the cause of failure and the examples selected are those that highlight aspects often under-appreciated in standard practice. Given the broad nature of geotechnical design and construction, focus is placed in this paper on onshore building projects where the author was involved as a post-incident reviewer or expert witness. The lessons learnt are equally applicable to large scale civil projects and offshore engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

The avoidance of failure is central to the role of engineers in all projects and is critical to the success (and sometimes survival) of any engineering company. It is, however, commonly assumed that the application of reasonable factors of safety to an engineering design is sufficient to ensure that failure risk is minimal. Despite this, failures continue to occur in geotechnical engineering applications. Details regarding the causes of such failures are not generally made known to the engineering community because of reputational damage to the companies involved and private settlements in litigation.

This paper aims to shed light on the nature of failures that continue to occur in geotechnical projects using case history examples taken from the author's life experience as a geotechnical engineer. Particulars related to companies and projects are omitted as the paper's primary aim is to highlight examples that can assist practitioners to avoid a repeat of previous failures.

Because of space limitations, attention is focussed in this paper on building-related projects. The case histories examined are divided into the following categories:

- Ground movements
- Vibration
- Unforeseen design conditions

- Water leaks/flow issues
- Inadequate site investigation
- Pile design
- Pile construction

The problems that arose in the case histories discussed could not be realistically anticipated from the geotechnical content covered in a typical civil engineering degree course and are illustrative of the importance of good experience, informed inquiry and attention to detail in the attributes of a geotechnical engineer. The lessons learnt can be added to the checklist that should be considered when signing off on design or construction drawings and methodologies for a new project. General conclusions gleaned from the cases histories with the author's perspective are provided in the last section of the paper.

2 GROUND MOVEMENTS

Engineers spend large amounts of time and effort to estimate the settlement of deep and shallow foundations and yet the author has encountered relatively few examples (discussed later) where settlements due to structural loads have caused significant issues. However, ground movements do not only occur due to dead and live loading of a structure's foundations and do not only occur in the downward direction. Two comparable illustrative examples are described

in the following where lateral ground movements have caused significant damage. Vertical ground movements are also discussed.

2.1 Apartment at soft clay site

This case history involved a two-storey apartment block in an area well known for its very soft ground conditions. The ground level sloped gently from the rear of the block towards a small stream, as shown in Figure 1a. The apartment was founded on 250mm square driven precast piles connected by ground beams.

Cracks began to emerge in the structure after a period of 6 months but residents noted a dramatic increase in crack widths on one particular day. An inspection shortly after showed that crack widths up to 20mm in width were present, which corresponds to the 'severe structural damage' category. Clear signs of building settlement (see brick separation on Figure 1b) and building rotation could be observed. In addition, tell-tales (such as recently cemented gaps) suggested that the block had moved laterally in the direction of the stream.

One excavation to the side of the block indicated the presence of a large void between the ground beam and ground level (Figure 1c). Confirmation of the significant lateral movement and building rotation became evident during excavation of another trial pit on one corner of the block (Figure 1d) where complete rupture of the (raked) corner pile had taken place and clear lateral translation of the building was apparent.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 1. (a) View of apartment and adjacent stream, (b) Evidence of settlement in brickwork, (c) inspection under floor slab and (d) Test pit on one corner of apartment

An understanding of the mechanism that caused the structural damage was required to ascertain whether the building could be repaired satisfactorily or if it should be demolished. Various investigations were performed including a review of the construction and post-construction history, monitoring of lateral soil creep movements (with inclinometers) and structural analysis to back-analyse the ground movements that would cause the observed structural distress. It was found that:

- The site contained a 8m deep deposit of extremely soft, compressible, estuarine clay with an estimated undrained shear strength of between 2 and 10 kPa. To provide a safe working platform for the piling rig, 1.5m of granular fill was placed on the site.
- The high compressibility and thickness of the soft clay led to a consolidation and creep settlement of almost 1m under the 30 kPa stress applied by the fill (as seen in Figure 1c).
- Inclinometer data indicated ongoing lateral movement in the direction of the stream.

- The site maintenance staff had imported substantial quantities of fill to maintain the level of car park at the front of the block. It was reported that a minimum of 200mm of topsoil and sand was placed every 6 months which is consistent with the observed settlement under the building.

Figure 2. Mechanism of lateral movement at site of apartment

This evidence points to the mechanism illustrated on Figure 2 which involves the lateral and downward movement of the soft clay ultimately leading to the structural failure of the corner pile and consequent significant cracking in the brickwork. Such a mechanism could easily be (and was) over-looked by experienced contractors and engineers.

2.2 Bridge abutment

An example similar to that of the apartment block arose after construction of a new rail bridge across a large river in Western Australia. In this instance, as shown in Figure 3, a 6m high embankment was constructed for the bridge approach instead of piling an approach structure. While this methodology is common in good ground conditions, the soil in the area comprised a 20m deep deposit of soft alluvium.

Figure 3. Approach embankment for bridge

Monitoring after bridge completion indicated that the rails continued to displace progressively and that the rail adjustment measures incorporated in the design were not sufficient to cope with the anticipated long-term movements. Engineers advising the authority responsible for the bridge operation stated that there was no solution to the ongoing creep of the alluvium and lawyers demanded that the contracting company demolish and replace the bridge unless another solution was found.

Figure 4. Approach embankment for bridge (a) Lateral creep movement under embankment fill, (b) remediation solution

To devise another more cost-effective solution required an understanding of the mechanism involved and accurate prediction of future behaviour. Finite Element analyses were performed using a range of constitutive soil models supported by appropriate laboratory strength and stiffness measurements. However, a simple observation indicated that the fill had caused both lateral and vertical movement and the lateral movement was being transferred to the steel piles supporting the abutment and hence caused movement of the bridge deck. (Figure 4a).

A ‘convocation’ of engineers with representatives from the transport authority, the contractor and the consultants was called and this committee subsequently agreed to the simple solution of installing ground anchors, as shown, in Figure 4b to pull back the abutment to its initial location. Additional stress could applied to the anchors to cope with future movements. The bridge is still operational 20 years on from when the anchors were installed.

The consulting engineer responsible for the design did not predict any significant level of lateral movement and therefore an important engineering lesson from this case history is that soil beneath an embankment moves sideways as well as downwards. The degree of lateral movement in this case was particularly high as the mobilised strength of the soft alluvium under the weight of the embankment was high (i.e. the factor of safety against a rotational slip was low).

The litigation for this case lasted 8 years and involved many lawyers and experts – so much so that the legal fees were almost comparable to the initial cost of the bridge.

2.3 Vertical ground movements

Vertical ground movements apply additional load to piled foundations due, for example, to ongoing creep settlement of soft soils or de-watering. The author has not personally come across incidences of pile failure due to vertical ground movements (although there are some reported cases in the literature e.g. Davisson 1993). The author has, however, reviewed many designs where the required ultimate design axial load has been incorrectly increased (often significantly) due to anticipated down-drag.

The additional axial pile load from down-drag due to the imposition of vertical ground movement is a serviceability limit state problem if the pile is structurally capable of carrying the structural load. A high down-drag causes the pile to settle and reverses the direction of friction (from negative to positive) providing added vertical resistance. The ultimate compressive capacity is therefore unaffected by vertical ground movements but an appropriate analysis needs to be conducted to ensure pile settlements under working conditions are acceptable. Vertical soil movements cause bending of raked piles which needs to be checked.

3 GROUND VIBRATIONS

The potential for damage to existing structures due to vibration from adjacent piling is well known (e.g. Massarsch and Fellenius 2014). Three simple cases are considered here which illustrate unexpected cases of vibration-induced damage.

3.1 Sheet pile installation

A 4.5m deep basement was proposed at a sand site, where one boundary was about 1m away from a 100-year old, single storey property. The client selected the cheaper option for the retention works of anchored sheet piles but was advised by the consulting engineer that vibration associated with the sheet pile installation would need to be minimised. The engineer

recommended the following vibration mitigation measures:

- Pre-install a 1m deep grout block to underpin the strip footings of the adjacent property
- Pre-drill augered holes to a depth of 3m at the location of sheets without removal of sand (to ease the sheet pile installation in loosened material)
- Initially push the sheet piles as far as possible through the pre-drilled holes, and then vibrate to 6m depth and impact-drive to the final toe depth.
- Conduct a dilapidation survey of the residence prior to sheet piling
- Install geophones at the property to monitor vibrations and halt installation if the peak particle velocity (PPVs) exceeded 4mm/s.

The sheet pile contractor implemented all of these recommendations. However, two days after sheet piling commenced over a weekend, the owner of the property notified the builder that cracks of up to 10mm in width appeared in the walls (e.g. as shown in Figure 5b). The builder immediately instructed the sheet piling contractor to halt work.

Figure 5. (a) Geophone records during sheet pile installation and (b) Cracks caused by sheet pile installation

Investigations into the activities around the time of the sheet piling indicated that:

- (i) No trial sheet piling and associated vibration monitoring was conducted. In fact, the sheet piling was commenced immediately adjacent to the property (i.e. the worst possible location).
- (ii) The vibrator employed did not have variable moment technology and therefore potentially harmful low frequency vibrations during start-up and shut down could not be avoided.
- (iii) Geophone data recorded by one geophone on the property are plotted on Figure 5a. It is seen that peak PPVs were often above 4mm/s and, in one instance, reached 12mm/s. Eurocode 3-Part 5, DIN 4150 and the Swiss standard indicate that a maximum PPV of 5mm/s (or 2.5 to 3mm/s for sensitive structures) is a safe upper limit for a masonry building such as the property.
- (iv) The PPV data were only inspected by the sheet piling contractor after the work was halted.

The simple message from this case history is that if the PPV data were examined during installation of the first sheet, it is likely that the sheet piling would have been abandoned and no damage would have ensued. Instrumentation data are, in the author's experience, often not acted upon quickly enough- as is the case for this project. The project was completed successfully using a secant pile wall.

3.2 Vibrated pile casings

A second example of vibration-induced movement in sand took place during installation of steel casings that provided temporary support in the upper soil horizons during drilling of 1.2m diameter bored piles. A contiguous anchored CFA piled wall (shown in Figure 6) was installed to provide support for a 6m basement. Piling was conducted from a platform at 3m depth while anchors were installed for the wall. Survey points were located on the wall as there was concern regarding movement of a gas main immediately behind the wall.

Daily monitoring of the survey points indicated ongoing wall movement, often as much as 10mm in a given day. The engineer initially considered that the movement was induced by the 3m excavation. However, it was obvious during a site inspection that casing vibration, as seen in the photo, was the source of significant movement. Installation of just six casings to 15m depth had caused the top of the wall to move by more than 25mm. No movement occurred when vibration ceased and casings were subsequently installed by rotary means instead. It is clear from this case history that the significant effects of casing vibration for the piles would not have been noticed if

the wall movement was not monitored and if the engineer had not visited the site. Fortunately, the rupture of the gas main behind the wall was avoided.

Figure 6. Vibrated steel casing adjacent to contiguous pile wall at a sand site.

3.3 Vibration due to dynamic pile testing

Large (1.6m diameter) bored piles were installed for a city centre development in the early 2000s. The project was abandoned for commercial reasons but was re-developed 10 years later. The engineers needed an indication of the pile capacity for the new development and commissioned dynamic pile testing of a number of the piles.

Reports of cracking in the slabs of the adjacent underground car park were obtained shortly after these dynamic tests were completed. Although the cracks were typically less than 1mm in width, they were extensive and hence there was concern that the durability of the slabs was compromised.

Even though only a small number of hammer blows were used in the dynamic tests, the energy required to cause some movement of the pile bases in these tests was significant (40 kJ). Application of a variety of standard attenuation relationships (Attewell & Farmer 1973, Heckman & Hagerty 1978) indicated that the peak particle velocities (PPV) induced on the basement car park by the testing could be expected to be in the range of 20 to 30mm/s. This PPV range is similar to the safe limit of 25mm/s recommended in the Australian standard for reinforced concrete structures and consequently the developer of the new property did not accept responsibility for the observed cracks.

As the standard attenuation relationships are for free-field conditions, a LS-DYNA dynamic numerical analysis was performed which modelled the dynamic pile test and the in-situ geometry, including the car park basement diaphragm wall. This analysis showed gave similar predictions of PPV to those of

the free-field attenuation relationships but predicted double the PPV values (up to 60mm/s) when the basement wall was included. This increase was due to effects of reflection from the wall magnifying the vibrations from the dynamic test.

In the end, the developer accepted responsibility and the repaired the car park slabs using an elastomeric sheet-applied membrane.

4 UNFORESEEN DESIGN CONDITIONS

This section presents examples of where the geometry assumed at the design stage of particular structures changed due to unforeseen circumstances and future adjacent developments.

4.1 *Shallow foundation at mine site*

One example where unforeseen design conditions caused significant alarm to a site operator arose at an Australian iron ore mine site. The iron ore at this site was transported via a conveyer system to the top of a 25m high stockpile from where it accessed a vault that gravity fed railway carriages; see Figure 7. The trains, which often had more than 100 carriages, brought the ore to the nearby port.

base of the stockpile encroached on the area occupied by the front foot of the ‘stacker’; see Figure 7b.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. (a) View of strip footing shortly after construction and (b) View of stacker and stockpile when vertical and lateral movements were significant

The operator had believed that the contractor who built the embankment beneath the stacker foundations was responsible for the movement. However, 3D Finite element analyses predicted the transfer of very large lateral loads, through arching, to the concrete plinths on the legs of the stacker (see Figures 7a and 8). High additional vertical loads, which were also not included in the design, were also transferred to the footings. The high creep rates of the footing arose due to the relatively high mobilised strength of the foundation soil.

Figure 7. Stacker system to convey ore to stockpile

It was observed a number of years after construction of the conveyer system that the strip footings at the front of the ‘stacker’ (see Figure 7a), which supported the portion of the conveyer system closest the stockpile, had settled and moved laterally, and that the movement was increasing with time. The operator estimated that the conveyer system would be un-serviceable within a couple of months if movement continued at the same rate – with a consequent associated cost of €800,000 per day. A solution was urgently needed and preferably one which did not halt operations.

A site visit revealed that the stockpile was operating at height greater than the maximum design height. This was prompted by the desire to transport greater quantities of ore. Consequently, the footprint of the

Figure 8. Mechanism causing footing translation and settlement

Having established the mechanism for movement, it was decided to inject cementitious grout into the foundation soils and to reduce the height of the stockpile to the design height. These measures halted any further movement of the stacker foundations which are still in operation 10 years later.

4.2 Deep basement construction adjacent to another basement

Unforeseen design conditions also led to extensive cracking of a heritage-listed church in Western Australia. A 4m deep basement was constructed adjacent to the church in the 1970s and, as shown on Figures 8a and 8b, employed a kingpost wall with two levels of anchors, each level with a total (free plus fixed) length of 6m. A new development at the same location entailed replacement of the single basement with a three-level basement and involved construction of a new diaphragm wall extending from the base of the kingpost wall to 5m below the new basement slab level (Figure 8c). Two additional levels of anchors were employed to provide lateral restraint to the diaphragm wall. The ground conditions comprised medium dense sand to a depth of 15m.

When excavation was nearing completion along one section of the diaphragm wall, the upper kingpost wall experienced a rapid lateral movement of about 300mm towards the excavation. This was accompanied by instantaneous settlement of the strip footings of the church and significant cracking both internally and externally.

The mechanism of failure was unforeseen by the designers of the new basement who installed a robust diaphragm wall and competent anchors. However, while focussing on the new portions of the basement, they neglected to assess the implications on the old basement wall. These implications are self-evident on Figure 8d which plots the location of the active wedge of sand adjacent to both walls. The original rows of anchors (installed to support the old single-level basement) were not long enough as all or part of their fixed lengths were within the active wedge associated with the deep excavation. As a consequence, the lateral restraint that they provide is compromised. Finite

element analyses subsequently showed that the observed rapid development of wall movements and ground settlements were consistent with failure of three of the top rows of anchors. The Church has since been repaired, but at considerable expense.

Figure 8 (a) & (b) Original basement adjacent to church, (c) Excavation for second basement, (d) Failure mechanism indicating anchor pull-out for top level of anchors

4.3 Impact of temperature changes

Steel props are commonly used to provide temporary support to deep excavations. One such project employed 600mm diameter, steel tubular props extending across a 24m wide, 12m deep excavation (Figure 9a). The props were welded to waler beams fixed to sheet piles used for the retention. The ground conditions comprised a loose to medium dense sand to 15m depth overlying alluvial clay and the water table was at 2m depth.

(a)

(b)

Figure 9 (a) Steel props supporting sheet pile wall, (b) temperature and prop force variation with time over three days.

The contractor had been provided with funds to assist a university research student and agreed to fix strain gauges and thermocouples on a number of the props and to locate an inclinometer and settlement plates on the outside of the excavation. The basement construction progressed satisfactorily with measured lateral movements and prop loads that were in line with the design expectations. However, a 200mm deep settlement trough was seen to develop progressively adjacent to the sheet piles over the course of about 2 months despite the excavation depth remaining essentially constant.

An example of monitoring data recorded for one prop over a period of three days is shown on Figure 9b. This shows prop temperatures varying between

15°C and 45°C and corresponding cycling of prop loads from 600 kN to 800 kN. The temperature induced prop loads arise due to the partial restraint provided by the sheet pile wall, which cycled into and away from the adjacent sand with a daily cyclic amplitude of 10mm. Cosgrove & Lehane (2003) show that similar cycling occurs adjacent to integral bridges abutments (due to brick deck expansion and contraction) and is the reason why run-on slabs are used to span settlement troughs that develop next to these bridges. The observed settlement of 200mm is therefore attributed to 60 daily cycles of ± 10 mm caused by thermal expansion and contraction of the props. This settlement caused damage to a concrete sewer but fortunately no other buildings were located within the zone of settlement. In hindsight, the contractor agreed that the props should have been insulated or, at the very least, painted white to reflect the sunlight.

4.4 Gravity retaining walls

On more than a number of occasions, the author has been requested to offer advice on where responsibility lies in cases where there is significant wall movement or wall distress following excavation, on the low side of a gravity retaining wall, some years after the wall was constructed.

The soil on the low side of a gravity retaining wall provides lateral passive resistance but also significantly enhances the bearing capacity of the soil. Given the prevalence of such failures, these contributions should ideally be excluded from design calculations and, especially so, when gravity walls are constructed close to property lines.

5 INADEQUATE SITE INVESTIGATION

Inadequate site investigations are well known to contribute to geotechnical failures. The examples considered here highlight how relatively simple errors in the site investigation can have a disproportionately large influence on a given project.

5.1 Building on swelling clays

The expansion and contraction of clays as they wet and dry is one of the biggest causes of damage to residential buildings. The damage costs the insurance industry several billion euro annually (British Geological survey www.bgs.ac.uk). The Australian Standard (AS2870) requires sites to be classified on the basis of the potential for clay shrink/swell and then obliges builders to adhere to specific construction practices depending on the site classification e.g. requiring use of deep pad foundations, stiffened slabs, articulation and wall reinforcement. Geotechnical site investigation companies undertake the site classifications and

employ sampling and dynamic cone penetration tests to assist in the classification.

Errors in site classification can have significant consequences. One example of this involved six, single storey brickwork town houses at a site in an arid region of Australia where the soils are generally sandy. A small geotechnical company conducted a number of 1.5m deep probes at the site and described the soil as a sandy silt. On the basis of the description, they classified the site as Class M, which corresponds to ‘moderate activity’. Cracking in the houses was noticed a year or two after construction was completed and got progressively worse. The damage 18 years after construction was classified as moderate to severe (Burland & Wroth 1974), with crack widths of up to 20mm.

Figure 10 Typical crack in one of the six properties in rural Australia (showing also a crack-meter used for monitoring)

A number of subsequent investigations at the site showed that the soil stratigraphy was not sandy silt and instead comprised stiff clay to a depth of at least 4m. A geological study showed that this clay is an alluvial deposit from an old river in the area. On inspection of the houses, it was found that the builder largely followed the recommendations of AS2870 for a Class M site (including placement of a 600mm sand bed across the site). However, under the impression that the soil was ‘sandy’, the builder disposed of the stormwater to 2.5m deep soakwells located in the (narrow) driveway at the front of the houses (see Figure 11a). As a consequence, the (dessicated) clay gradually swelled and caused the front sides of the houses to heave and cracks to develop in the brickwork (see Figure 11b).

Figure 11 (a) Soakwell arrangement for stormwater and (b) mechanism causing cracks

The significant damage caused by the clay heave (and the subsequent repair costs with 18 years of legal bills) can be attributed to the error made in the initial site investigation that probably took a single operator a couple of hours to conduct. The input of engineers to developments such as that described is generally minimal and, as a consequence, such errors are not uncommon in the author’s experience.

5.2 Poor desk study

The importance of an adequate desk study is well understood by geotechnical engineers. One of the first examples of the importance of desk studies witnessed by the author involved a new apartment building in London in the mid-1980s. The geotechnical engineer specified 4 boreholes at the site, as shown in Figure 12, and each borehole indicated a stratigraphy typical of central London, namely Thames gravel overlying London clay. Based on this stratigraphy, it was decided that 2.5m square pad footings founded in the gravel were the most suitable foundations for the apartment. However, on excavation for these footings, it was found that a 20m by 20m central area of the site contained loose domestic landfill. Subsequent investigations indicated that this fill extended to a depth of at least 8m and that the local council records

had shown that the site was a designated tip area. This fact would have been easily ascertained in an adequate desk study. The apartment was founded on piles after a long delay and at a major cost to the consulting engineering company.

Figure 12 (a) Borehole investigation at London site and (b) Cross-section through the site

5.3 Unusual soil characteristic

Although this paper deals with building projects, one civil case is considered here to illustrate the importance of careful attention to detail during a site investigation. This project required construction of a 8m high road embankment and the site investigation indicated that the stiff clay was present from ground level to large depths. No stability issues for the embankment were foreseen until a final series of trial pits along the alignment were conducted just prior to construction. These pits were logged by an experienced geologist (and by the author in sub-zero temperatures!) and revealed the presence of low-friction slicken-sided surfaces at a depth of 2 to 3m. Such surfaces are common in high plasticity montmorillonite-rich clays (for which the residual friction angle is usually less than 10°) and have a profound effect on embankment stability.

Following this discovery, a total re-design of the embankment was required, necessitating the use of geogrid reinforcement and lightweight fill. The additional design and construction cost of the embankment led to a series of claims and counter-claims and an eventual out-of-court settlement.

6 WATER LEAKS/FLOW ISSUES

Many geotechnical failures involve water. This is because water can impose high pressures on structures

and can also cause erosion with high flow rates. Some examples from the author's experience are provided in the following.

6.1 Secant piled wall

Secant piled walls are an accepted form of retention for basements constructed below the water table. However, a recent example in Australia highlighted a key shortcoming of such walls.

A secant pile wall was used to enable top-down construction of a 18m deep, 5 level basement at a sand site with a water table close to ground level. A jet-grout 'plug' was first installed at a depth of 24m which was then followed by the secant pile installation to the same depth. The plug was intended to reduce the quantity of water seeping into the excavation during construction.

Figure 13 Configuration of deep basement construct using secant piled walls

It became obvious during the excavation that water was seeping through small gaps in the secant piling. De-watering requirements became progressively larger as the excavation depth increased and finally pumps were turned off and the basement was allowed to flood. The basement was de-watered 6 months later when the weight of the superstructure was sufficient to balance uplift pressures that would act on the basement raft after it was cast and pumps were turned off.

The gaps between the secant piles arose due to the difficulty in maintaining pile verticality for such a deep excavation. Although not visible, it was inferred that larger gaps existed between the piles beneath the basement slab level and that, even with good control of verticality, the risk of gaps forming in a deep secant pile wall are high.

The secant pile walls above excavation level were shotcreted. However, seepages continued at the slab-wall connections and a number of ‘blow-outs’ in gaps in the secant pile wall occurred and needed to be plugged. The building is now in service but the annual cost of pumping to maintain a dry basement is excessive and can be expected to increase with time as water flow continues to widen the gaps between the piles. Cracking and deterioration of the piles is expected to increase due to ongoing rusting of the reinforcement (in the saline environment with access to air in the basement). Water seepages at the slab-pile connections will also compromise their structural integrity. Remedial solutions are currently being explored with one solution being to construct an entirely new reinforced concrete wall inside the secant piled wall (at considerable expense).

6.2 Slab connection to diaphragm wall

A 15m deep basement was constructed using a diaphragm wall (D-wall) with temporary propping at a site with a high water table in Western Australia. Although the Contractor had a wealth of experience in D-wall construction, on excavation, significant leakages through the walls were observed at the levels of the permanent slabs.

A typical detail employed at a slab to D-wall connection is shown on Figure 14a. The reinforcement cage of the D-wall panel includes couplers to ensure continuity of the wall and slab steel. After concreting the D-wall and subsequent excavation, the plywood sheets used to protect the face of the couplers are removed to allow the slab steel to be introduced.

For this particular project, the slabs were only 250mm in thickness and large quantities of steel were specified at the D-wall slab connections because of the high bending moments predicted at these locations. The D-wall included bending, shear and secondary steel as well as the couplers for the slab steel connection. The end result is evident in Figure 14b which shows excessive congestion with little opportunity for the D-wall concrete to self-compact in the small available space between the steel. Water under high pressure from outside the wall continued to flow through the voids in this area at an ever-increasing rate.

The Contractor remedied the situation by epoxy grouting all the connections. There was, of course, long delays to the construction programme and associated costs. The long term durability of the connections remains uncertain.

Figure 14 (a) Typical arrangement for connection between diaphragm wall and slab and (b) Congestion of reinforcement leading to voids in the concrete and leaks.

6.3 Unexpected water flow induced damage

A new two-level basement in Perth, Australia, was constructed at a sand site adjacent to a residence founded on strip and pad footings. The basement was constructed using a contiguous bored pile wall because the water table level was well below the deepest excavation level.

Cracking appeared in one corner of residence shortly after completion of the basement and its owner, understandably, attributed the damage to the basement construction works. No agreement emerged between the parties regarding the mechanism causing the damage as the cracks continued to widen well after the basement was completed.

Crack monitoring was commissioned and showed that cracks widened in the wintertime but no movement was recorded over the summer months. It is noted that about 700mm of rain falls in Perth in the June-September (winter) period and conditions are essentially dry for the rest of the year.

Subsequent exploratory test pits in the cracked area of the residence uncovered a broken stormwater

sewer used for collection of rainfall on the roof. Rain-water was evidently progressively eroding the sand supporting the footings causing their settlement, with one pad footing almost completely under-mined. As the broken sewer section was just on the line of the piling for the basement, the piling contractor accepted responsibility for the damage, admitting that the outcome of the case was most unexpected.

6.4 Further cases involving water flow/leaks

Water flow/leaks are a common cause of failure and other examples that the author has had direct experience of are when:

- A joint between a slurry wall and D-wall was breached by water under high pressure due to unanticipated relative movement of the walls.
- A dewatering pump which was used to keep an excavation dry caused water flow that eroded the heads of grout piles that had recently been cast.
- Installation of a grout curtain installation next to a river was un-successful as the river carried the grout away from the curtain location.
- Poor lapping detail on a geomembrane for a large sea bund led to the creation of water pathways and progressive erosion of the bund.
- Incomplete grout coverage of a permeable layer caused inundation of tunnel excavation and collapse of the overburden.

High water pressures and permeable soils or pathways within the soil represent a dangerous combination. In these circumstances, particular care in detailing is required to ensure the integrity and safety of any substructure.

7 PILE DESIGN ISSUES

7.1 Pile set-up

The first example considered here relating to pile design involved driven steel pipe piles for a bridge abutment. The piles were 970mm diameter with a design embedment of 15m in medium dense sand. Pile dynamic testing conducted on a number of piles immediately after pile driving indicated a compression capacity of 4 ± 1 MN. However, as the design required a capacity of 4.5 MN for all piles, the Contractor elected to extend all the piles an additional 5m, founding the piles in a stiff clay layer (Figure 15a)

Figure 15 (a) Stratigraphy at site of driven piles for bridge (b) Observed set-up of shaft friction for driven piles in sand (Bittar & Lehane 2024).

The designer responsible for specification of pile toe depth of 15m was charged with the additional time and cost associated with extending the piles. However a review of the literature showed that ageing of shaft friction of piles in sands is significant and increases at a rate of at least 25% per log cycle in time; e.g. see Figure 15b which plots the ratio of measured shaft friction to capacity calculated by the Unified CPT method (ISO-19901-4 FDIS, 2024) against time after driving.

A meeting of experts set up for the litigation agreed that the decision to extend all piles was not taken with proper consultation with the designer, who was subsequently cleared of responsibility for the extra costs.

7.2 Effects of stress relief

A 5-storey apartment with a two level (6.5m) basement was constructed at a medium dense sand site where the water table was just below the basement slab level. 6m long, 600mm diameter continuous flight auger (CFA) piles, installed from the basement level, supported the superstructure and were designed

using Bustamante & Gianeselli (1982) CPT correlations.

Significant differential settlements (in excess of 100mm) and cracking in the structure was observed towards the end of construction and this was shown to be due to large pile settlements. Various reasons such as unusual ground conditions and over-flighting during CFA pile construction were mooted until the design calculation for pile capacity estimations were examined.

These calculations showed that the piles were designed based on the cone resistances measured *prior* to the excavation works and not the cone resistances that would have been measured if cone testing was conducted at excavation level. This effect of stress relief was particularly pronounced as the pile lengths were relatively short. A new set of pile capacity estimates were derived using q_c values adjusted on the basis that the relative density remains unchanged by excavation and cone resistance varies with the current horizontal effective stress raised to the power of 0.7 (allowing for the effects of overconsolidation on K_0). The revised estimates of capacity were only about half of those calculated assuming the original q_c values.

The under-estimation of capacity was exacerbated by the use of the Bustamante & Gianeselli (1992) recommendation to adopt a pile end bearing of $0.45 \pm 0.05 q_c$. This is because a database of CFA pile tests compiled by Lehane (2009) and Doan & Lehane (2021) showed that end bearing at 10% of the pile diameter in sand is typically only about 0.16 ± 0.04 times the q_c value i.e. close to one third of the Bustamante & Gianeselli (1992) prediction.

The cost of repairing the structural defects that occurred as a result of the two critical errors in the design assumptions were borne by the designer.

7.3 *Over-reliance on dynamic testing*

18m long, 900mm diameter bored piles were installed at a sand site and subsequently tested dynamically. Wave equation backanalyses (CAPWAP) from two dynamic tests indicated pile compression capacities of about 7 MN and a pile head displacement at the working load of 3.2 MN of about 3mm. However independent assessment of the pile capacity using well established (and local) correlations suggested that the pile capacity was only about 4.5 MN and that the settlement under the working load would be about 15mm. The contractor argued that ‘good pile installation techniques’ explained the high capacities measured in the dynamic tests. The client agreed but requested that monitoring of the pile settlements be undertaken during construction. Settlement monitoring was undertaken and confirmed the applicability of the local correlations with individual piles settling by between 15mm and 20mm. Interestingly, the building

did not show any significant distortion as the differentials were essentially built-out of the structure as it was constructed. The effect of increasing building rigidity reducing differential settlements is a very beneficial effect that is not often considered. The contractor, in this instance, did not suffer as a consequence of the over-estimate in pile stiffness and capacity.

8 PILE CONSTRUCTION

8.1 *Concreting using a tremie pipe*

Concreting of large diameter piles is almost always conducted via a tremie pipe initially positioned at the base of the bore, where the bore is usually supported by either bentonite or polymer ‘mud’. The tremie comprises sections, typically 3m in length, which are removed progressively as the surface of the concrete in the bore is raised and the drilling fluid is displaced upwards by the concrete.

One particular bored pile project that the author was involved with employed 1.2m diameter, 40m long concrete bored piles, constructed using a polymer support fluid. Cross-hole sonic logging was used to assess the integrity of the concrete in about 10% of the piles. This logging revealed anomalies where, at a number of elevations in a number of piles, the travel time between the cross-hole emitter and receiver was substantially slower than sound concrete. This finding caused alarm to all involved in the project as the piles were required to support a 30-storey structure.

Diamond coring of the piles was commissioned to ascertain the extent of the issue and to determine if remediation of the piles was possible. One example of a 5m length of core retrieved is shown on Figure 16b and, in this case, indicates the presence of a 100mm long void (with soil infill). Further cores taken in the same pile showed that the void was not continuous across the pile cross-section, which was of significant relief to the designers.

A typical view down the bore of a pile under construction is shown on Figure 16a. Inspection of the tremie pipe revealed the cause of the voids in the piles. It was seen that the O-ring seals between the sections of one set of tremie pipes used in the project, which were not of the threaded variety, were missing in some cases. Further investigations confirmed a correlation between piles with occasional voids and those constructed using this set of tremie pipes. It was then clear that the polymer drilling fluid was seeping through the tremie pipe joints into the pipe itself during pauses in concreting. When a new concrete truck arrived, the delivered concrete entrapped the polymer present in the pipe into the pile. These entrapped zones were then observed as low strength zones in the cross-hole logging and as voids in the cores.

Significant lengths of core were extracted from the constructed piles on the project to confirm the extent

of the pile defects, causing a delay of 3 months to the construction programme. Defects were detected in about 20 piles and these were remediated by pressure grouting using down-the-hole packers.

Figure 16 (a) View down bore of bored pile during construction, (b) Concrete core (5m) retrieved from bored pile

8.2 Insufficient concrete head

One of the author's early experiences with construction-related defects involved foundations for an office development in London in the 1980s. The foundations were 15m long, 450mm diameter piles constructed using standard bored piling techniques. The bores were supported by temporary casing in the upper 8m of the profile (comprising made ground and Thames gravel) and were self-supporting in the underlying London clay; the water table was at about 4m depth. A particular feature of this project was that the piles were installed prior to excavation for a two-level basement and therefore the trim (cut-off) level of the piles was about 7m below ground level. The piling contractor was therefore motivated to save concrete and to halt concreting when the concrete level in the bore was just above the design trim level.

Following completing of the piling and the basement excavation, further excavations for the pile caps were conducted. These revealed, as illustrated in Figure 17a, that much of the concrete in the upper 2m of about half of all the piles on the project was missing.

Figure 17 (a) Appearance of bored pile after excavation for pile cap (b) Differential head causing displacement of wet concrete in the pile.

A review of pile construction records revealed the cause of the defects. The author extracted the poured concrete volumes and pile toe levels and then estimated the final level of the concrete in the temporary casing in each pile. A clear correlation between this level and defects in the piles emerged, as seen on Figure 18 i.e. defects are far more prevalent when the final level of the cast pile was lower. It could then be inferred that the high water level relative to the concrete level caused the wet concrete to be displaced when the temporary casing was withdrawn (Figure 17b).

Figure 18 Relationship between relative difference in level between the water table and the concrete level in the casing

The defects led to a major re-design of the structure with a different footprint and the appointment of a different piling contractor to install a new set of piles.

8.3 Further cases involving pile construction issues

Pile construction issues are relatively common compared with design issues. Disputes and legal cases that the author has provided advice on briefly summarised as follows:

- (i) Driven pipe piles were employed for a jetty in SE Asia. However, the dip in the rock level at depth was such that the piling contractor could not achieve the specified location and inclination tolerances.
- (ii) Precast concrete piles were used as foundations for a storage tank in Melbourne, Australia. Dynamic tests on the piles, which were driven to a dense sand layer, indicated lower capacities than recorded at the end of driving. This unusual behaviour was proven to arise because of the close proximity of the piles and the consequent uplift of adjacent piles during driving.
- (iii) Driven closed-ended pipe piles were used for a development in SE England where ground conditions comprised interbedded sand and clay layers. The piles were bottom driven and therefore thin-walled piles were deemed sufficient, particularly as they were to be infilled with reinforced concrete. It was found, however, that driving had caused implosion of adjacent piles, which had not been infilled. Almost all piles on the project were installed before the damage was discovered. Bottom driven piles are not commonly used, in the authors experience.
- (iv) Helical (screw) piles are often not load tested as the torque required for installation can be used to

assess their axial capacity. A static compression load test was performed on one such helical pile (with a helix diameter of 380mm) where it underwent a settlement of 100mm at just 1.2 times the service load. A re-test and subsequent exhumation of the pile show that the helical plate had sheared off from the shaft i.e. the pile experienced a structural failure and not a geotechnical failure.

- (v) Continuous flight augered (CFA) piles were installed in loose sand overlying weakly cemented sand. During augering of the piles, it was found that the ground in the vicinity of the piling rig had settled by almost one metre. This arose because of the relatively poor torque capacity of the particular rig employed which over-flighted when augering through the cemented sand. The over-flighting (i.e. a high ratio of pile rotation relative to pile penetration) essentially compacted the overlying loose sand, causing the settlement.

9 CONCLUSIONS

It is certainly easy in hindsight to see how the failures mentioned in this paper could have been avoided. In the author's opinion, the main contributory factors to the failures are as follows:

- Cost pressures creating constant demands on engineers to produce designs in both a cost-effective and timely manner.
- Lack of oversight where critical aspects are overlooked because of excessive focus on other aspects of the project.
- Lack of experience in certain areas with little consultation with experts.
- Lack of testing where no trials or tests are conducted to reduce risk and uncertainty (often because of time and cost constraints)
- Pressure from other members of the design and construction team to produce quick answers and solutions
- Accepting low budgets for ground investigation and design
- Not performing adequate research, background reading and desk studies
- Poor communication amongst all parties

While geotechnical engineers strive to do the best job possible, it is important to be self-critical to understand how improvements can be made. Observed shortcomings of *some* of the engineers involved in the case histories described were those who:

- Did not know what they didn't know
- Assumed somebody else would take responsibility
- Did not read enough to develop expertise and knowledge
- Went straight to conducting Finite Element analyses without understanding the critical issues
- Focussed on processes & quality of reporting but missed important elements
- Communicated poorly (and rarely picked up the phone !)

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In conclusion, it is important to be aware that:

1. Every design & construction method carries risk. All parties should be made aware of the risks.
2. Risks are evaluated objectively by keeping an open mind and consulting widely. All assumptions should be documented and relayed to the project team.
3. Nobody is immune from design & construction errors, failures and claims. They occur all the time and ideally are resolved before lawyers are involved.

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